

APPENDIX 1

Below the fossil calibrations are listed that were used in the empirical angiosperm example.

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Teucrium_chamaedrys_1kp*, *Ruellia_brittoniana_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 38.4Ma

Taxon: *Catalpa sp.* ID = 303 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Nicotiana_heterantha_Ang353*, *Solanum_sisymbriifolium_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 52.2Ma

Taxon: *Physalis_infinemundi* (Wilf et al. 2017)

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Galium_boreale_1kp*, *Pteleocarpa_malaccensis_Ang353*

Minimum age constraint: 41.2Ma

Taxon: *Emmenopterys_dilcheri*. ID = 297 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020).

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Vahlia_capensis_Ang353*, *Teucrium_chamaedrys_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 79.7667Ma

Taxon: *Scandianthus_costatus*. ID = 59 from Magallon et al. (2015).

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Forgesia_racemosa_Ang353*, *Quintinia_oreophila_Ang353*

Minimum age constraint: 79.7667Ma

Taxon: *Silvianthemum_suecicum*. ID = 82 from Magallon et al. (2015).

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Echinops_sphaerocephalus_Ang353*,

Acicarpa_tribuloides_PAFTOL

Minimum age constraint: 72.1Ma

Taxon: *Tubilifloridites_lilliei*. ID = 328 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020).

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Cyrilla_racemiflora_Ang353*, *Solanum_sisymbriifolium_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 86.3Ma

Taxon: *Paleoenkianthus_sayrevillensis*. ID = 55 from Magallon et al. (2015).

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Nothofagus_obliqua_1kp*, *Comptonia_peregrina_Ang353*

Minimum age constraint: 93.9Ma

Taxon: *Normapolles*. ID = 218 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Elaeagnus_pungens_1kp* *Rhamnus_caroliniana_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 72.1Ma

Taxon: *Coahuilanthus_belindae*, ID = 234 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020).

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Polygala_lutea_1kp*, *Gilbertiodendron_ecoukense_Ang353*

Minimum age constraint: 56Ma

Taxon: *Leguminocarpon_gardneri*, ID = 209 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020).

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Ruptiliocarpon_caracolito_Ang353*, *Euphorbia_pekinesis_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 86.3Ma

Taxon: *Paleoclusia_chevalieri*, ID = 221 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020).

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Upuna_borneensis_Ang353*, *Arabis_alpina_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 86.3Ma

Taxon: *Dressiantha bicarpellata*, ID = 239 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020).

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Litchi chinensis_1kp*, *Upuna borneensis_Ang353*

Minimum age constraint: 89.8Ma min = eleven_on_original 89.8

Taxon: *Sapindospermum nitidum*, ID = 260 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Staphylea trifolia_1kp*, *Crossosoma californicum_Ang353*

Minimum age constraint: 56.0Ma

Taxon: *Staphylea minutidens*, ID = 240 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA *Terminalia neotaliala_1kp*, *Syzygium paniculatum_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 86.3Ma

Taxon: *Esgueiria futabensis*, ID = 248 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA *Saxifraga fortunei_Ang353* *Myriophyllum aquaticum_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 89.3

Taxon: *Divistylus brevistamineus*, Hermsen et al. (2003)

Calibrated node: MRCA *Nepenthes mirabilis_Ang353*, *Polygala lutea_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 100.5

Taxon: *Dakotanthus cordiformis*, ID = 325 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA *Buxus sempervirens_1kp*, *Trochodendron aralioides_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 110.8

Taxon: *Lusistemon striatus*, ID = 184 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA *Ceratophyllum demersum_Ang353*, *Polygala lutea_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 127.2

Taxon: *Montsechia vidalii*, ID = 358 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Strelitzia reginae_1kp*, *Anigozanthos bicolor_Ang353*

Minimum age constraint: 72.1Ma

Taxon: *Spirematospermum chandlerae*, ID = 149 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Panicum miliaceum_1kp*, *Deschampsia cespitosa_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 66Ma

Taxon: *Changii indicum*, ID = 144 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Typha angustifolia_1kp*, *Strelitzia reginae_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 83.6Ma

Taxon: *Sabalites carolinensis*, ID = 129 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Butomus umbellatus_Ang353*, *Strelitzia reginae_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 123.0Ma

Taxon: *Mayoa portugallica*, ID = 4 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Aristolochia elegans_1kp*, *Piper auritum_1kp*

Minimum age constraint: 72.1Ma

Taxon: *Aristolochiacidites viluiensis*, ID = 175 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Lindera_benzoin_1kp*, *Magnolia_acuminata_Ang353*
Minimum age constraint: 113Ma
Taxon: *Endressinia brasiliiana*, ID = 10 from Ramirez Barahona et al. (2020)

Calibrated node: MRCA of *Amborella_trichopoda_Ang353*, *Polygala_lutea_1kp*
Minimum age constraint: 132.5Ma
Maximum age constraint: 145.75Ma
Taxon: Various angiosperm pollen grains, ID = 1 from Magallon et al. (2015)

APPENDIX 2

Figure S1

Figure S1. Percentage error for mean posterior estimates of r in analysis of data from the simple four-taxon simulation where all simulated data is analysed, and different percentages of the gene trees are topologically incongruent with the species tree. The correct species tree topology is the same as that shown for the species tree in Figure 1, and the topologically incongruent gene trees have the same topology as shown in Figure 1. **a)** refers to estimates of r for internal branches in the species tree when r is estimated with a relaxed clock with high variance. **b)** refers to estimates of r for internal branches in the species tree when r is estimated with a relaxed clock with low variance. **c)** refers to estimates of r for terminal branches in the species tree when r is estimated with a relaxed clock with high variance. **d)** refers to estimates of r for terminal branches in the species tree when r is estimated with a relaxed clock with low variance.

Figure S2

Figure S2. Percentage error for mean posterior estimates of r when analysing data from the simple sixteen-taxon simulation with a balanced species tree and where all simulated data is analysed. Numbers above branches refer to estimates when r is estimated with a relaxed clock with high variance. Numbers below branches refer to estimates when r is estimated with a relaxed clock with low variance. When the percentage error is below 5%, no value is shown. The tree displayed refers to the species tree. Two terminal labels indicate where the topology of the incongruent gene tree differs from the topology of the species tree, with the grey right hand tip label referring to the topologically incongruent gene tree. In all cases 50% of gene trees have the incongruent gene tree topology, and 50% of gene trees have the species tree topology. **a)** is a special case where the incongruent gene tree is identical to the species tree. The incongruent gene trees for **b-e)** exhibit sequentially higher levels of topological incongruence.

Figure S3

Figure S3. Percentage error for mean posterior estimates of r in simple sixteen-taxon simulation experiments with an imbalanced species tree and where all simulated data is analysed. Numbers above branches refer to estimates when r is estimated with a relaxed clock with high variance. Numbers below branches refer to estimates when r is estimated with a relaxed clock with low variance. When the percentage error is below 5%, no value is shown. The tree displayed refers to the species tree. Two terminal labels indicate where the topology of the incongruent gene tree differs from the topology of the species tree, with the grey right hand tip label referring to the topologically incongruent gene tree. In all cases 50% of gene trees have the incongruent gene tree topology, and 50% of gene trees have the species tree topology.